

Halli Mane Rotties - A Case Study on Woman Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

Women entrepreneurship is identified as the one where all the factors of production marketing and management is undertaken wholly by a woman or group of women. Women entrepreneurs contribute significantly to economic growth and employment generation. The new generation women, across the globe, have undertaken risks, faced challenges and have proved themselves beyond doubt in all spheres of life including the most unmanageable world of entrepreneurship. This is a case of woman entrepreneurship of Ms Shilpa who runs Halli Mane Rotties in Mangaluru city. Ms. Shilpa had faced all the challenges and succeeded as an entrepreneur of repute. Her enthusiasm, self-motivation for success and willingness to deliver more than expected by customers have brought her to the present state where she is the heroine of a success story. Her distinctiveness in business are; homely food in streets, non usage of color and additives and use of handpicked vegetables and groceries

Key words: Challenges, Innovation Women Entrepreneurship, Work Life Balance.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is an economic activity which is undertaken by an individual or group of individuals. It is the process of designing, launching and running new business, which is often initially small business. Entrepreneurship emerges from an individual's creative spirit into long term business ownership, employment creation, capital formation, economic security. The people who create and run these businesses are called entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial skills are essential for industrialization. Women entrepreneurship is the process where women organize all the factors of production, undertake risks, and provide employment to others. The definition of women entrepreneurship has never been differentiated on the basis of sex

and hence could be extended to women entrepreneurs without any restrictions. A woman entrepreneur is one who starts business and manages it independently and tactfully, takes all the risks, faces the challenges boldly with an iron will to succeed. Women entrepreneurship is an economic activity of those women who think of a business enterprise, initiate it, organize and combine the factors of production, operate the enterprise and undertake risks and handle economic uncertainty involved in running business enterprises. This case is about the woman entrepreneur Ms Shilpa, owner of Hallimane Rotties Mangalore.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the case of individual women entrepreneurship in Hallimane Rotties.
- To ascertain the core problem and challenges of an individual woman entrepreneur.
- To study the work life balance initiatives of a woman entrepreneur

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the study primary and secondary sources of data was used. For the primary source, personal interview was conducted with the woman entrepreneur in Halli Mane Rotties, Mangaluru. For Secondary sources and information from Journals, articles newspaper, internet, books and concerned business have been used. After the interview, the analysis of the case was done in respect to different factors like Social, Economic, Competitive, and Locational Mobility of the entrepreneur.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Women entrepreneurship, with development of business sector, has grown up rapidly in the last decade. When we talk about women entrepreneur, the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs need to be trained and addressed by the educational institutions especially in terms of business planning and inculcate of managerial skills, Rao, Venkatachalam & Joshi (2012). woman entrepreneur, entrepreneurial skill help her to get an identity for herself and be respectful in the eyes of the society. Woman is not confined to home base business they are equally trained to work in the main activities of the business whether it is a service or manufacturing unit Hemanth Kumar P. Bulsara, Jyothi Chandwani, Shailesh Gandhi(2014).P. Sinduja A and M. Ashokan (2016) reveals that SWOT analysis of Woman entrepreneur. Mainly woman entrepreneur success because of confident and high achievement motivation, weakness is focused on absence of proper support and co-operation by her own family

members, woman entrepreneur avail lot of opportunities and government supporting woman empowerment schemes., threat is fear of expansion of business and losses. Hemanth Kumar P. Bulsara, Jyothi Chandwani, Shailesh Gandhi(2015) study examines woman entrepreneur had overcome all the challenges and become one of the most successful woman entrepreneur of the city. According to them strategies of industrialization often depend upon the emergence and development of entrepreneurial skills and appropriate environment.

HALLIMANE ROTTIES, MANGALURU

The Genesis

Ms Shilpa hails from Hassan and belongs to an affluent agriculturist family. Shilpa had moved to Mangaluru along with her 3-year-old son in 2005 to live with her husband and subsequently got her parents and brother Chiranjeevi too. In 2008, her husband Rajshekar, a city-based businessman and the sole breadwinner of the household deserted her and left to Bengaluru. He disconnected himself from Shilpa leaving her and her family depressed and heart broke. To make a living, she started working as a housemaid for some time to meet the family expenditure and also to get over the fatal tragedy. She even worked for a beauty parlor as a saleswoman and other petty occupations earning salaries that were not at all sufficient to take care of her family. Shilpa lost all hopes of giving her family an ideal life but fate had some other plans.

The Startup of ‘Hallimane Rotties’

Shilpa was very much interested right from her childhood in cooking Malnad style of food which she inherited from her mother. Having kept this in mind, Shilpa thought why not turn her passion into a venture, and this led to the birth of a new venture – “**Halli Mane Rotties**” in Shilpa’s life. With a very optimistic idea in hand, she reluctantly had to withdraw the fixed deposit of Rs.100000 that she had set aside for her son’s education. In the initial stage, Criticisms hovered over Shilpa which even made her think that bringing Malnad delicacies to the coastal region is a bad idea, but that’s the only cuisine she knew. Despite all the odds, in 2015 Shilpa began with “Halli Mane Rotties” leaving the critics and herself dumbstruck looking at the positive response from the locals. Shilpa never looked back ever since.

Shilpa's determination and belief in herself made her achieve the place where she is today. The lady who worked under others is now a well-known entrepreneur.

Operation and Customers

The eatery is situated at Mannagudda Mangalore and operates between 4 P.M to 10 P.M every day. It is visited by various customers every day and yields daily turnover Rs 3000 to Rs 7000. Shilpa says, “Nearly 80% of my clients are locals from Dakshina Kannada. Then there are Doctors, students, IT professionals who are looking for Home food”.a few tech-savvy student patrons have been mapped shilpa’s food truck on the Google search engine, giving it an online visibility. People looking for homely food find Halli Mane Rotties as their ultimate destination.

Products

The vegetarian delicacies of Malnad include Akki Roti, Ragi Roti ,Methi Roti ,Kayi Holige, Lemon Rice, Bisibelebath(Hot Lentil rice’), Thatte idli, Tomato Omelet etc. Non veg items available are Chicken Roast, Chicken Donne Biryani and Chicken Green Masala.

Looking Forward

This inspiring entrepreneur has her vision in opening a new outlet which would extend her the delicious food to people in a different place and also would add as a helping hand for her brother to sustain independently.

Competency of Business

The key to please the customers lies in the ingredients used for cooking which she gets all the way from her hometown Hassan. The concept of healthy street food is all that Shilpa wants to promote. She added that she avoids food colour or additives to her food which gives it a homely taste.

Work Life Balance

Family including her son is an integral part for Shilpa. This successful entrepreneur balances both her career and home with the support of her family members. “ As the day goes, the entire family involves to work. While vegetables and groceries are procured by my parents, my brother and, I turn to run the mobile stall. Besides, I have to look after my 12 years old son too” Shilpa says.

Recognitions

Shilpa is the owner and chef of the popular Halli mane Rotties, a mobile fast food outlet and her inspirational successful journey recognized by Executive Chairman of Mahindra group Anand Mahindra who has gifted a Bolero Maxi Truck, to this inspiring food woman

entrepreneur. Shilpa is a recipient of Mahindra Transport Excellence Award 2017 for her achievements.

ANALYSIS OF THE CHALLENGE FACTORS

On the basis of the discussions and perceptions following factors are arrived at:

Table 1

Factors	Sub factors	As perceived by entrepreneur
Social factors	Childhood	Much interested in cooking Malnad side food.
	Religion	Hindu
	Education	S.S.L.C
	Family	Her son, brother and parents
	Work life balance	Yes, its challenging
	Positive strength	Support from family
Economic factors	Financial support from institutional sources	No, did not take any help
	Business location	Mannagudde, Mangalore
	Material	From her hometown Hassan
	Size of the market	Mangalore nearby places through mobile eateries
Competitive factors	Potential competitors	Yes , to some extent
	suppliers	No,
Locational mobility of entrepreneurs	Resources	Yes, available
	Languages	Yes, to some extent
	Culture	No
	Nature of enterprises	Canteen

Source: Discussion with the entrepreneur

Social Factors

Jyothi Chandrawani, Hemanth Kumar P. Bulsara, Shailesh Gandhi (2015) in their study found that woman entrepreneur family not trust her financial capabilities to maintain the business. In Present study Shilpa coming from Agriculturist family, had faced lot of challenges to start up her business and after setup the activities of businesses managed effectively by support from family as their full involvement. She says “work life balance is challenging”

Economic Factors

Arrangement of finances for the startup of the business is yet another challenge for women entrepreneurs. Different Government schemes are available, but there are bottle necks and gaps. Appropriate financial information is not available to women entrepreneurs. Even Ms Shilpa had financial problem to start up her business. She had utilized money kept for her son’s education. She received Rs 95,000 from Udyogine Yojana. She purchases major materials from her hometown Hassan and other materials from Mangalore. Size of the market expanded to nearby places in Mangalore.

Competitive Factors

High competition with established self-sufficient entrepreneurs. The ambition, self-confidence, experiments, innovative motives, risk bearing ability is essential qualities for the success of entrepreneurs. But lack of trust in the capabilities of women entrepreneur faces problems from supplies, buyers and potential competitors because they have lack of trust in their capabilities. In this study Ms. Shilpa did not experience any competition at the beginning from existing food outlets because her concept to satisfy the customers like to keep the food homely as she does not mix any additives, or taste or colour to food. But now a days though we find many grown up competitors, they are the first person to name as Hallimane , as they find many people who follow this name in many places.

Locational Mobility of Entrepreneurs

In this case reveal that resources were available easily. As she was born and brought up in Hassan, after marriage shifted to Mangalore, to some extent faced language problem to communicate with Mangalorean customers.

CONCLUSION

The case suggests that women can play an important role in the economic development of the country and also command respect and progress. Ms Shilpa manages her food outlet in an

extraordinary way and commands good business. She has entrepreneurial capacities as risk taker, decision maker and marketing stalwart. She is indeed, an inspirational to all, especially the women folk. She is a homemaker turned into successful woman entrepreneur as running one of the renowned mobile eateries.

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